

THE IMPACT OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT ON STUDENT'S

ACHIEVEMENTS IN WRITING CLASSES.

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Abstract: This article is about examining the impact that formative assessment has on student learning and improving writing skills. In addition to this the writer find out significant information about the history of formative assessment. In the article it is clearly understood that formative assessment methods that are used in the classroom positively impacts student learning.

Keywords: Formative assessment, proficiency, assists, psychological behaviour, inference, nuisance, consciousness, creativity, confidence, preparedness, enhance.

One of the greatest undertakings that teachers participate in with students is helping to ensure students understand and learn the content being covered. Call it part of the job, responsibility, obligation or duty, but teachers play a major part in ensuring students leave the classroom with a knowledge of what has been covered so that students can continue an education to ultimately contribute to society in the vocation of their calling, for the glory of God. Formative assessment is a powerful way that teachers can help in this endeavor. It is a way to gauge what students know versus what is unknown. Traditionally, the typical way that teachers and students have been informed of the learning that has taken place was through summative assessment, a test that is given at the end of a chapter or a unit to measure what students understand and know from the instruction that has taken place. Grades are generally given out to students, depending on how well the student did on these tests, and then teachers and students alike move on to the next phase of the curriculum. Formative assessment is altogether different in that it, “gives teachers information that they can use to inform their teaching and improve student

learning while it is in progress and while the outcome of the race can still be influenced”.

While thinking about the historical background of this assessment we should highlight the person who firstly used formative assessment. Michael Scriven coined the term formative assessment in 1967. Scriven wrote about an evaluation process for the goal of improvement and called this process formative. The formative process explains that, “while a program is in the planning and developmental stages, it is still malleable, and the information gathered from evaluation can therefore contribute to change in the program”. From this time on, the term formative assessment has been used in educational settings as a way to inform teachers on student learning while the learning is taking place. With the use of formative assessment practices, teachers have been able to use information that has been gathered to make the necessary adjustments and changes with the hope that students would master content. Fisher and Frey lay a foundation in which a teacher understands the importance of establishing a comprehensive formative assessment system. This system has three parts that involve learning goals, student feedback, and the planning of student instruction based on identified weaknesses or errors. Fisher and Frey contend that when a comprehensive formative assessment system has been established and is used consistently, teachers will be able to identify students’ strengths and remedy weaknesses in order to achieve a higher level of student learning.

Students’ learning achievement depends upon the foundation of writing. This basic tool that is used for the assessment and assessment helps the teacher to make inferences about students through it. The items that are written properly can provide proper and correct data about the performance and learning of the students. The written items become useful for a teacher to make sound decisions regarding instruction. The proficiency

of the student can be checked through writing. The skill and practice is required for the assessment of the writing items.

It is well-known fact that formative assessment assists in English writing skills, and the students face difficulties in improving English writing skills. Special lectures and trainings may be managed for English writing skills and give a specific focus on writing skills during formative assessment.. Moreover, psychological behaviour that is related to the assessment is also help in designing writing items. In this study, the researcher has decided to explore the effects of the formative assessment in the improvement of English writing of the students of college level. A great difficulty is faced by the students while writing English essays, dialogues, stories and paragraphs. The complicated structure of English grammar creates a nuisance for students or English learners.

The role of assessment can be effective for the teachers in their teaching and also for the learners. Creativity in writing is totally ignored, and there is no improvement in the quality of the writing. The students have not a lot of vocabulary; therefore, they cannot produce new ideas in the English language while writing it. The new approaches which are introduced in the modern or present curriculum have a great focus on the formative assessment. There is a dire need to show the consciousness of the teachers about the problem of the students in there writing. At the college level, it is very necessary to introduce a strong and exact way of writing. Authorities, paper setters, examiners, teachers and curriculum maker should coordinate with one another to remove the clash between learning outcomes and assessment. Creative writing, critical thinking and analysis about writing is a big requirement at the college level. The students who ignore to learn their writing at the secondary level face difficulties at the college level. They have no idea to write anything accurately. They have no competency on self-writing. They make many grammatical mistakes while writing an essay, paragraph, stories, and dialogues. The aim of this study to explore

the difficulties faced by the students regarding their writing and to give them proper feedback using formative assessment. To enhance the writing performance of the students at the college level, it is needed to understand the difficulties faced by the students. According to Imen Zahaf , formative assessment has an impact on the progress of students in their learning in general, and in their writing skill in particular. By one hand, the analysis of the student's questionnaire shows their interest in the writing process. On the other hand, the teachers' questionnaire revealed that the implementation of formative assessment in the writing classroom is necessary and important to enable learners to enhance their writing production and to reduce some difficulties they are facing during the writing process. Due to the difficulties students are still facing in their writing, a set of suggestions were recommended in this study for the written expression teachers to reduce the writing problems students are struggling with and offering opportunities for learners to practice more and more as far as it motivates them to produce well in written texts. Written expression teachers should focus on what materials are given such as: giving notes, copies, portfolios and so on in order to meet their students' need and make the teaching effective. ¹⁵⁵

In conclusion all studies advocate that formative assessment positively impacts student learning. Along with this, statistics show that students believe formative assessment increases confidence, learning, and preparedness. Teachers can benefit from the use of formative assessment to help inform their teaching and to help identify what students know versus what is unknown. Students can benefit from the use of formative assessment as well to more effectively determine what content is understood and to also serve as a guide to what needs to be improved upon.

¹⁵⁵ Govt. of Pakistan, 2009.

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